

Unusual Oxidation States of Silver : Ag (III) Complexation to I-Amidino-o-alkylurea, Piperazinedibiguanide and Related Ligands

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Only a few coordination complexes of silver(III) are reported in the literature. Among the ligands tried biguanide and ethylene-dibiguanide are the classic examples for stabilization of Ag(III)^{1,2}. We have undertaken a programme to investigate the effect of electronic and steric requirements for stabilization of +3 oxidation state of silver and we report in this preliminary communication several new silver (III) complexes with 1-amidino-o-alkylureas (R = methyl, isopropyl, *n*-butyl, and isobutyl) and piperazinedibiguanide.

Silver (III) complexes of 1-amidino-o-alkylureas and piperazinedibiguanide were prepared in the form of sparingly soluble brown or orange-yellow crystals of the composition [Ag(LH)₂](SO₄)_{1.5} (where LH = a molecule of 1-amidino-o-alkylurea or 0.5 mole of piperazinedibiguanide) by oxidising the aqueous solution of silver (I) sulphate or nitrate and ligand sulphate with potassium persulphate at pH 6.5-7.0. The complexes were found to be diamagnetic at room temperature as expected for Ag(III). The diamagnetism also indicates the dsp² hybridization in these complexes. These Ag(III) complexes oxidise two equivalents of iodide ion per gram-atom of silver indicating Ag³⁺ oxidation state in these compounds. The mull spectra of these complexes exhibit two peaks in the ultraviolet and visible region, one having band maximum around 260 mμ, and the other appearing as a shoulder in the descending part of the spectrum. The corresponding ethylenedibiguanide complex exhibits a broad peak at 300-370 mμ¹. It is interesting to note that potassium persulphate oxidation of silver (I) salts in presence of these ligands always resulted in producing silver (III) complexes, and we are not yet able to isolate any bivalent silver complex. These silver (III) complexes as well as the corresponding ethylenedibiguanide and biguanide complexes undergo photolytic decomposition. If these complexes are exposed to direct sunlight or diffused light of the laboratory, the colour of the complexes fade slowly.

In order to extend the number of compounds containing the higher oxidation states of silver, we tried other isoelectronic ligands like amidinourea, 1-amidino-2-thiourea, biuret and dithiobiuret. Among these ligands only amidinourea has been found to stabilize the silver (III) state. The present study confirms the observation of Ray and Sen¹ that ethylene bridge is not necessary to stabilise the silver (III) state.

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Isolation of other salts of the complex cations and characterisation of the complexes by I.R., N.M.R. (with heteronuclear spin decoupling), photoelectron spectroscopy, dilution conductivity and polarographic studies are in progress. Preparation of Ag(III) complexes utilising other quadridentate biguanides (*e.g.*, hexamethylenedibiguanide etc.) and other substituted 1-amidino-*o*-alkylureas is progressing.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Amidino-*o*-methylurea sulphate, 1-amidino-*o*-isopropylurea sulphate and 1-amidino-*o*-butyl (iso- and normal) urea sulphates were prepared and purified according to the published procedures^{3,4}. Piperazinedibiguanide sulphate was prepared according to the method of Ray and Choudhury⁵. Mull spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Cary 14 recording spectrophotometer.

General method of synthesis of the complexes: One hundredth mole of silver (I) sulphate* (2.0 g) was dissolved in 20 ml. of water by gentle warming. The appropriate amount of the ligand (as sulphate salt) used was weighed out for a 1 : 3, Ag : ligand complex (1 : 1.5 in case of piperazinedibiguanide). This was dissolved in minimum amount of water and the Ag (I) solution was added to this with stirring. This was then mixed with aqueous potassium persulphate solution (3 g in minimum amount of water). The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6.5–7.0 with dilute NaOH or saturated NaHCO₃ solution, and was then slightly warmed on a hot plate and stirred vigorously for few minutes. The resulting deep coloured precipitates were suction filtered and washed thoroughly with aerated cold water, and dried in a dark desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. The preparations of the complexes were done in a dark room to avoid photolytic decomposition of the complexes.

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* Silver (I) nitrate may also be used in place of silver (I) sulphate.